

IMPLICATIONS OF SCHOOL HEADS' CLASSROOM OBSERVATION TO ELEMENTARY TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL COMPETENCE AMIDST PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The scope of the study was to find out the relationship between classroom observation and teacher's instructional competence. One hundred fourteen (114) selected elementary teachers at the district of Tiaong, Division of Quezon. It was purposive sampling from elementary teachers at the district Tiaong, Division of Quezon. It was used the percentage, mean, standard deviation, correlation coefficient and ANNOVA. The perceived level of classroom observation in terms of observation techniques verbally interpreted very important, teacher's involvement verbally interpreted absolutely essential, feedback mechanism verbally interpreted very important and evaluation process verbally interpreted very important and the perceived level of instructional competence in terms of classroom management, assessing students' progress, instructional strategy, remediation, were all verbally interpreted very highly competent. There are significant relationships between classroom observation and teacher's instructional competence however, classroom management as an instructional competence is related to classroom observation of the principal in terms of her evaluation process. The researcher concluded that there is a significant relationship between classroom observation and teachers' instructional competence therefore, the hypothesis is not sustained and there is significant predictor of teacher's classroom management competence on school head's classroom observation therefore, the hypothesis is not sustained.

Keywords: classroom observation, classroom management, student progress, instructional competence